

Digital Divide Initiatives Taken by Government of India and New India Literacy Programme

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Abstract	The paper reviews that digitization divides with the internet is a very important part of information acquisition and communication. Due to COVID-19, the global pandemic affected people provided by administrators through digital media. Digital services and the internet were used for education, transactions, money and shopping. The Union Cabinet has approved a "New India Literacy Programme" for school to college level with the aim of changing the term "Adult Education" will be replaced by "Education for All".
Keywords	Information Resources, Internet, Information Communication Technology, Education
Introduction	The digital divide is a social issue between rural and urban India underlying referring gap between those who do not have the same privileges and access to modern (ICT) information communication technology. It is also shown that disparities between certain regions and demographics. It also indicates differences in economic, social levels or other categories between information communication technology and the internet. India has the largest growing Internet user, and vivid gaps exist. All the programs undertaken by Gol are delivered to citizens in gram panchayats, electronically, healthcare, financial education, deliver services, land records, justice and promoting e-governance etc. The government of India plans to cover 31 mission projects under the e-governance plan, including things such as banking services, postal, tax, law, municipalities, passport, education, health, land records and agriculture.
Objective of study	<p>The objectives of NILP Components are given below:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Continuing education: including science, technology, adult education, arts, culture, yoga, sports and recreation, mediation as well as other topics. 2. Basic education: including pre-primary, middle, and secondary education 3. Vocational skills & development: towards obtaining local employment for vocational skill's development. 4. Critical life skills development: including family education, health education, digital literacy, financial literacy, commercial skills and child care and awareness. 5. Foundational literacy: New India Literacy Programme to impart foundational literacy and numeracy, but other components which are required in the 21st century.
Review of Literature	<p>Various books and online literatures i.e. Avgerou, C., & Madon, S. (2005) Information Society and the Digital Divide Problem in Developing Countries, Billon, M., Marco, R., & Lera-Lopez, F. (2009) Disparities in ICT adoption: A Multidimensional Approach to Study the Cross-country Digital Divide, Chinn, M. D., & Fairlie, R. W. (2007). The Determinants of the Global Digital Divide: A Cross- Country Analysis of Computer and Internet Penetration, Diamond, L. J. (2010) Liberation technology. Journal of Democracy, Gunkel, D. J. (2003). Second thoughts: toward a critique of the digital divide, Gupta, R., & Jain, K. (2015) Adoption behavior of rural India for mobile telephony: A multigroup study etc have been studis and reviewed for this paper.</p>
Main Text	<p>The government of India has taken some initiatives.</p> <p>The government of India to bridge the gap between the empowerment of citizens using pioneering technology digital divide, with transform India's aim to connecting knowledge and economies.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Article 21 of the Constitution of India: The Supreme Court of India has declared a fundamental right to access the Internet, right to education, right to privacy. 2. NeGP: It was launched in 2006, to citizens through common service centres (CSCs), to enhance transparency, reliability and efficiency for government services. 3. The BharatNet Project was launched in 2011 to connect India's villages through (100 mbps) optical fiber and connect 0.25 million Panchayats. 4. The National Mission for the Delivery of Justice and Legal Reforms: Gol launched in 2011, leveraging ICT to provide fair and easy access and reducing delays in the legal system.

5. M-Kisan: it was launched in 2013 to provide information and advisories through SMS, inform farmers about better agricultural practices and location.
6. Digital Saksharta Abhiyan was launched in 2014 by the Government of India National Digital Literacy Mission.
7. Digital India: it was launched in 2015 by the Ministry of Urban Development, to bridge the urban-rural digital divide, business, ICT and jobs.
8. The Smart Cities Mission was launched in 2015 to develop 100 smart cities in India using Information Communication Technology and best practices in urban planning.
9. SEHAT: It was launched in 2015 by Gol in collaboration with Apollo Hospital, a pan-India health service for 60,000 CSCs in the country for healthcare services.
10. E-NAM: launched in 2013, an electronic portal to help farmers with advanced schemes, weather-related updates, crop production techniques, different markets and prices.
11. PM Gramin Digital Saksharta Abhiyan was launched in 2017, to usher in digital literacy in India's urban and rural areas, covering 60 million households.
12. BHIM: It was launched in 2016 to facilitate quick and easy online financial transactions. "National payment corporation of India has launched Bharat Interface for Money" (BHIM).
13. National Education Policy-2020: new education policy launched by the government of India with changes from school level to college with multiple levels of entry and exist on digital education.
14. The Internet Saathi Program was launched in 2015 by Tata Trusts and Google India with the aim of women digital literacy education in rural areas.
15. Optical Fiber Network: a project by the Government of India (NOF-N) to ensure broadband connectivity approx. two lakh Gram panchayats of India.
16. DIKSHA: a platform was launched in 2017, school education in all over India (state & central government) from class 01 to 12. School education in India is considered a Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing platform includes 'one nation; one digital platform'.
17. National Digital Literacy Mission or Digital Saksharta Abhiyan and Pradhan Mantri Gramin Digital Saksharta Abhiyan (2018a). Digital literate at least one person in every Indian family.
18. Unnati Project: "Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited" provides access to computer education for rural students, social background and poor economics to bridge the digital divide in schools.
19. Digital Mobile Library: a project introduced by the Government of India in collaboration with the Centre for Advanced Computing, Pune to bridge the digital divide.

New India Literacy Programme

The government of India has launched a "New India Literacy Programme" from the Financial Year 2022-27 to cover all aspects of adult education to align with NILP. The term "adult education" will be replaced by "education for all", a centrally sponsored scheme. The Minister of State for Education provided information about the NILP. The age group of 15 years or above 5 crore non-literates covers a target.

Identification of Beneficiaries:

States/UTs conducted surveyors to identify beneficiaries for a door-to-door survey on a mobile application.

Directly register non-literates through a mobile application.

Implementation Technology Scheme covers:

1. The DIKSHA platform by NCERT is used to access teaching and learning resources and materials through a mobile application.
2. Online Teaching Learning and Assessment System (OTLAS), NIOS and NCERT.
3. Implemented predominantly online through volunteerism, this scheme is based on modern technologies.
4. Face-to-face mode may be organized workshops, orientation programmes and training. All the study materials are available online resources and provided digitally.
5. School units will be conducting surveys of voluntary teachers and beneficiaries

Information Dissemination of Foundational Literacy

Dissemination of foundational literacy modes used, like Samajik Chetna Kendra, Radio, TV, and Mobile.

Need of NILP:

Non-literates of the country absolute age of 15 years or above age groups.

Saakshar Bharat programme, adult are still non-literate in India.

Conclusion

The Government of India's National Education plans for school to adult education literacy programme have parallel elements. The education systems across the world are providing training for children and adults. So, that they can learn to read and write smoothly and improve skill development. Information communication technology has improved connectivity across the world. The ICT adoption and use correlates capabilities in India

and observed income, household demographics and education are strong determinants of the differences in education, gender, age, categories after controlling for ICT access.

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